

IMMUNITY IS THE GUARANTEE OF HEALTH IN MEDICINE

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Abstract:

Immunity is the ability of our body to recognize and then destroy foreign substances, thereby protecting itself from various external and internal threats. First of all, such threats include infections.

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Introduction

Immunity is the ability of the body to resist infection and fight against diseases. And increasing immunity is a way to strengthen health.

What is the immune system itself? The immune system or immunity is the system and ability of the body to protect itself from foreign substances, cells, including bacteria and viruses. A weakened immune system can make people vulnerable to a variety of things. This process is caused by various factors. The weakening of the immune system can be caused not only by a lack of certain vitamins or minerals, but also by improper organization of your lifestyle and daily routine. quickly affects the system. Antibodies in the blood are composed of immunoglobulin proteins, and for their normal production, the diet should contain enough meat, eggs, fish, dairy products, and legumes. In addition, when nervous fatigue occurs, the hormonal system that regulates the activity of immune protection fails. As a result, immunity weakens. Also, chronic lack of sleep, harmful habits, such as smoking, alcohol consumption, obesity, and a sedentary lifestyle are also among the main reasons for a decrease in immunity in a person.

Of course, the external environment also has an impact on immunity. Harmful production enterprises, air pollution, radiation are among them.

The complications are many. With the decrease of immunity, various weakenings are observed in the body. This can lead to frequent illness. And even during the year, the number of colds increases significantly. If the immunity is strong, any cold will pass quickly. The body quickly overcomes viruses and bacteria using drastic protective measures. However, due to low immunity, the intestinal system is disturbed. This causes symptoms of dysbacteriosis, alternating constipation and diarrhea, flatulence, frequent heartburn. Also, frequent recurring rashes, unhealed wounds, cold sores, and allergic diseases also occur as a result of immune system disorders. In addition, due to decreased immunity, weakness, lack of energy, decrease in labor productivity can also be observed. In this case, even if a person sleeps enough, he does not get enough sleep.

The diet is the first priority. According to it, first of all, it is necessary to refrain from salty, spicy and fatty foods. It is better to limit the consumption of products containing sugar and caffeine. Instead of them, it is recommended to eat pumpkin, carrots, beets, tomatoes, onions, garlic, greens, dairy products, apples, citrus fruits, lean meat, fish and honey. These delicacies saturate the body with minerals and vitamins and strengthen the immune system.

Avoid lack of vitamins. Onion is one of the products that increase the body's ability to fight against diseases. It helps to fight against microbes that have entered the body, stop the growth of cancer cells, and increase immunity. Garlic onion helps to restore the body after stress, cleans the liver. It is an excellent tool for fighting inflammation and tumors. Vitamin C also strengthens the immune system. It is found in large quantities in lemons, lemons, oranges, sweet peppers, and black currants. Ginger is also a product rich in minerals and vitamins, which quickly strengthens the body's resistance to diseases. In addition, consuming a teaspoon of honey a day is also beneficial for health. However, people who are prone to allergies and suffer from chronic diseases should consult their doctors before consuming these products. What should be done for the normal functioning of the immune system?

Go to bed at the same time every day

It is necessary to learn to go to bed at the same time every day, regardless of what time it is, this will allow you to fall asleep quickly and get complete rest.

If you go to bed earlier or later, the body cannot adapt to the change in rhythms, resulting in superficial sleep. At least 8 hours a day should be devoted to sleep, because the body needs that much time to recover. Start the day with a cup of tea. The substances contained in blue or black tea are able to effectively fight against the cold virus. 2-3 cups of tea a day are enough. Take action as soon as the first signs of flatulence appear. Folk medicine can be used for this. Add honey and lemon juice to crushed raisins and walnuts and mix. As soon as you start noticing the first symptoms of a cold, eat this mixture three times a day for 1 tablespoon.

In addition, adding honey to namatak decoction and drinking it also has a great effect during a cold.

Drink enough water Due to the fact that most of the body consists of water, it needs a certain amount of water every day. Scientists set this norm as 8 glasses. Body as a result of dehydration

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